

TERRITORIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TRADITIONAL RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS IN UZBEKISTAN (KHORAZM AND BUKHARA)

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In this article, the territorial characteristics of traditional residential buildings in Uzbekistan are highlighted on the example of traditional settlements of Khorezm and Bukhoro, mainly using natural methods to create a microclimate and develop regional architecture.

Key words. *Taskhhovli, porch, right porch, reverse porch, corridor, tobiston, zimiston.*

O'ZBEKISTONDA (XORAZM VA BUXORO) AN'ANAVIY TURAR-JOY BINOLARINING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI.

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi an'anaviy turar-joy binolarining hududiy xususiyatlari Xorazm va Buxoroning an'anaviy aholi punktlari misolida, asosan, mikroiklim yaratish va mintaqaviy me'morchilikni rivojlantirish uchun tabiiy usullardan foydalangan holda yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. *Toshhovli, ayvon, o'ng ayvon, teskari ayvon, yo'lak, tobiston, zimiston.*

ТЕРРИТОРИАЛЬНАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ЖИЛЫХ ЗДАНИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ (ХОРАЗМ И БУХАРА)

В данной статье на примере традиционных поселений Хорезма и Бухары освещены территориальные особенности традиционной жилой застройки Узбекистана, преимущественно использующие естественные методы создания микроклимата и развития региональной архитектуры.

Ключевые слова. *Ташховли, крыльцо, правое крыльцо, обратное крыльцо, коридор, тобистон, зимистон.*

Based on the climate and historical-ethnographic region of each region of our country, residential buildings have their own architectural features and views. In particular, the architecture of Khorezm residential buildings differs from other geographical areas. For example, the "Taskhovli" palace was built by Ollokuli Khan in Khiva near the eastern gate of the city - Polvon Darvoza. Due to the climate of the city of Khiva, special importance was attached to the construction of verandas in the construction of the "Tashkhovli" palace. The verandas built against each other helped to keep the microclimate of the inner courtyard cool.

Fig 1. "Ters" and "O'ng" ayvans of the "Taskhovli". Source: <http://xorazmiy.uz/uz/khorezm>

In this case, the porch built on the north side is higher than the porch built on the opposite side. This process provides cool air in the courtyard during the hot summer heat.

The main purpose of the construction of the verandas is that the climatic conditions of Khorezm are sharply continental. In the city of Khiva alone, architects designed and built houses in different styles depending on their location. A second porch was built on the opposite side of the porch, and these porches were called the right porch and the opposite porch. Ters (inverted) porch is so named because it faces back (north), that is, opposite to the qibla. The right porch faces the Qibla. Depending on their appearance, porches are also called "Big, big" and "small, small" porches. Some people understand the porch facing the Qibla as a reverse porch. According to the words of older people, the wind that entered the courtyard with two verandas could not come out and hit the walls of the veranda on the right and opposite sides, creating a cool microclimate. [Development history of residential buildings in Khiva "Science and Education" Scientific Journal/ ISSN 2181-0842 April 2022]

Fig 2. Part of a residential house with “O’ng” and “Ters” ayvans. Example from researcher.

Another type of porch is named "Urganch" porch. The Urganch porch (in some sources it is called a corridor) is located in the middle of the yard and is surrounded by rooms on all four sides. There is a tall pillar in the middle of the porch. In some cases, it leads to the garden through the door on the north side of the porch. Urganch porch, like other porches, is built 1.5-2 meters higher than the common house, and large windows are placed on all four sides at the top. This, in turn, ensured the light of the house. [Development history of residential buildings in Khiva “Science and Education” Scientific Journal/ ISSN 2181-0842 April 2022]

Fig 3. Khorazm. Dwellings with Dolon. Example from researcher.

The residential types in Bukhara are also developed, they are densely built, they are facing the courtyard, separated from the street, the rooms are one or two stories, and

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are surrounded by the courtyard. densely built, and thus it was much cooler in the courtyard than in the hot and dusty air of the street. The Bukhara residential type usually started with a covered corridor far beyond the gate. Corridors used in Bukhara served a different purpose than the corridors used in residential areas in Khorezm. Cool air is provided through the corridor to escape from the scorching heat of the street until reaching the inner courtyard through a long covered corridor (like a tunnel). Dolon is not only a unique shade and cooler, but also has a wind deflector mechanism. Indeed, the function of the corridor in the field of housing construction was important. In its place, it also played the role of a vestibule. In addition, the additional construction area served as a shelter during the rains. Dolon was mostly used in city yards. After the corridor, there is an entrance or gatehouse (sometimes the gatehouse was built before the corridor). At that time, houses were divided into "outer" and "inner" yards. One of the reasons for this is: under the influence of the beliefs of the Islamic religion, it is to protect women "from prying eyes", and the second is; the custom that appeared long before that is the division of the yard into economic (outside) and cultural (inside) parts. Also, the construction of the rooms facing only the side of the yard has a two-sided character. That is, the first thing is that the windows and doors do not open to the outside (to the street); if it is within the framework of Sharia, secondly; it is to exclude the yard from external noise, dust, etc., and build it towards the trees and flowers in the yard.

The basis of Bukhara houses consists of two parts - winter and summer. Winter (Summer) is a part of the house porch and is the main living area. And summer (Zimiston) - the cold part of the house, mainly located under the house or 1.5 meters above the ground. Such rooms in Bukhara were also called Tobiston and Zimiston.

Fig 4. Example of Bukhara dwellings with the “Tobiston” and “Zimiston” parts. Example from researcher.

To sum up, traditional dwellings in Uzbekistan have their own territorial features, and the Khorezm grand porch has adapted to the hot region by creating a microclimate in the courtyard, acting as a wind trap. Traditional residences of Bukhara have summer rooms with high ceilings and cooling holes from the basement. South walls are usually double-layered, this method is called "double chinch" and aims to reduce the solar radiation on the south walls and prevent the internal walls from overheating. The winter rooms and the winter rooms are small and the ceilings are not too big, so heating the rooms is easy. All such traditional approaches indicate that the residential architecture is adapted to the climate and that there are elements of stability.

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